

Full Paper

Influence of Fluorinated Surfactant Composition on the Stability of Emulsion Drops¹

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Aqueous drops of a well-defined size are often used as small containers for conducting chemical and biochemical reactions, cell assays, and as templates to produce microparticles. To prevent their coalescence, they must be stabilized for example using surfactants. We compare the ability of different nonionic di- and triblock copolymer surfactants to stabilize water drops that are dispersed in fluorinated oils. In particular, we look at the influence of the length of their hydrophilic poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) block on the drop stability. The stability of drops coated with triblock copolymers scales with the interfacial tension, whereas that of drops coated with diblock copolymers scale with their packing density. Surfactants whose ratio of the radii of gyration of PEG to the hydrophobic block (FSH) is between 0.54

¹ **Supporting Information** is available online from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

and 0.67 impart the best stability to aqueous drops not containing high salt concentrations. By contrast, surfactants whose ratio of the radii of gyration is between 0.34 and 0.37 impart the best stability to aqueous drops containing high salt concentrations. Hence, the choice of the best surfactant strongly depends on the composition of the fluids.

1. Introduction

Aqueous drops are often used as pico- or even femtoliter sized vessels for conducting chemical reactions,^[1] polymerase chain reactions (PCR),^[2] manipulating genes,^[3,4] cells,^[5-8] viruses,^[9-12] or small organisms,^[5] and as templates for the production of microparticles of a well-defined size and composition.^[1] Many of these applications require drops with narrow size distributions, which can conveniently be produced using microfluidics.^[13] If intended for biological applications, aqueous drops are usually formed in perfluorinated oils because they are biocompatible^[14-16] and have a high gas solubility.^[17,18] Additionally, they are compatible with poly(dimethyl siloxane) (PDMS),^[19] an elastomer routinely used to fabricate microfluidic devices,^[20] which greatly facilitates their operation. To prevent coalescence of emulsion drops, they must be stabilized for example by adding surfactants, which adsorb at the liquid-liquid interface, thereby lowering the interfacial tension between the aqueous phase and the oil and imparting steric stability to the drops.^[18] Drops can be stabilized with commercially available poly(perfluoropropylene glycol)-carboxylates; however, the charged carboxy group can interact with biomacromolecules, risking a change in their conformation and therefore a loss in their function.^[15,18] To overcome this limitation, perfluorinated polyether (PFPE) blocks have been covalently linked to uncharged hydrophilic blocks, such as PEG^[21] or poly(methyl glycerol).^[22] The resulting block copolymers impart good stability to aqueous drops at room temperature. As a result, this type of surfactant has been commercialized^[23,24] and is often employed for biological^[5,25] and material science^[26] applications. However, the stability of drops coated with this surfactant is significantly lower if kept at elevated temperatures. As a result, in many cases, drops coalesce at elevated temperatures even though, under certain conditions, some drops remain intact. The reduced drop stability at elevated temperatures can be assigned to the decrease in the solubility of PEG with increasing temperature, which leads to a change in its conformation that negatively

affects the surfactant quality.^[27,29] This is inconvenient because common applications, such as PCR,^[2] or in some cases the conversion of drops into particles^[28] require heating drops to elevated temperatures. Moreover, in many cases, this surfactant fails to stabilize drops containing high salt concentrations because the solubility of PEG also decreases with increasing salt concentrations.^[29] This is inconvenient because salts are required for experiments conducted under physiologic conditions, making the use of these drops for many biological applications difficult. To improve the stability of drops subjected to these demanding conditions, more efficient surfactants must be developed. The efficiency of nonionic amphiphilic block copolymer surfactants to stabilize aqueous drops in hydrocarbon-based oils has been shown to depend on the length of the PEG block.^[21] Whether similar principles also apply for fluorinated surfactants remains to be determined. A better understanding of this correlation would facilitate the choice of an appropriate surfactant and enable tuning the drop stability to the requirements of the specific application.

In this paper, we investigate the influence of the length of the PEG block of nonionic di- and triblock copolymer surfactants on their ability to stabilize aqueous drops in fluorinated oils. Surfactants whose radii of gyration of the PEG to the hydrophobic block (FSH) is between 0.54-0.67 impart the highest stability to drops containing no salt. By contrast, surfactants whose ratio of radii of gyration of PEG to the hydrophobic block is between 0.34 and 0.37 impart the highest stability to salt-containing drops. Remarkably, drop stability cannot unequivocally be related to the interfacial tension or surfactant packing density: While the stability of drops coated with triblock copolymers increases with decreasing interfacial tension, that of drops coated with diblock copolymers increases with increasing packing density. Thus, the choice of the surfactant that results in the highest drop stability strongly depends on the exact composition of the fluids.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Surfactant synthesis

We synthesize fluorinated surfactants following a previously established protocol.^[21] We dissolve 1 mol equivalent of the perfluorinated polyether Krytox FSH 157 (7000 Da, Chemours, USA) in a fluorinated oil, Novec HFE-7100 (3M, USA) at 0.1 g/ml, and degas the solution using argon. The carboxylic end group of the FSH is activated by adding 10 mol equivalent of thionylchloride (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) to the solution and refluxing it at 65°C under inert conditions for 2 hours to form an acid chloride end group. Unreacted thionylchloride is removed from the solution by increasing the temperature to 90°C for 1 hour under reduced pressure, before we cool it to room temperature and re-dissolve it in HFE-7100. To remove traces of water from the hydrophilic block we dissolve 1.1 mol equivalent, for diblock copolymers, or 0.57 mol equivalent, for triblock copolymers, in trifluorotoluene (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) at 0.1g/ml and heat the solution to 130°C; this is done for monofunctional amine-terminated PEG (Jenkem M_w 295 Da, 5000 Da) and Jeffamine (Huntsman, Jeffamine M-600, M-1000, M-2005) and for homobifunctional amine-terminated PEG (Jenkem M_w 368 Da, 600 Da, 5000 Da) and Jeffamine (Huntsman, Jeffamine ED-600, ED-900, ED-2003). After cooling the product to room temperature, we add anhydrous dichloromethane (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) until all PEG is dissolved. To scavenge the HCl, which forms during the coupling reaction of the amine group with the acid chloride end group from the activated FSH, we add 1.5 mol equivalent of triethylamine (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) to the PEG solution. This solution is mixed with a HFE-7100-based solution containing the activated Krytox FSH and refluxed overnight at 65°C under inert conditions. The solvents are subsequently evaporated at 65°C under vacuum. The resulting surfactant is purified from unreacted PEG by dispersing the final product in a mixture of HFE-7100 and

methanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The ratio of the solvent must be adjusted to the molecular weight of the hydrophilic block to prevent dissolution of the surfactant, but ensure dissolution of the unreacted PEG. To accelerate the sedimentation of the immiscible surfactant from the dispersion phase, the mixture is centrifuged at 3000 g and 3°C for 15 min (Mega Star 1.6R, VWR) and the supernatant containing unreacted PEG chains is subsequently removed. This process is repeated three times before the surfactant is dried using a rotary evaporator (Hei-VAP, Heidolph, Germany) and freeze dried (FreeZone 2.5, Labconco, USA). We analyze the surfactants using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Nicolet 6700, ThermoFisher Scientific, USA), as shown in **Figure S1-S9**.

2.2. Interfacial tension measurements

The interfacial tension is quantified using the pendant drop method performed on a drop shape analyzer (Krüss, DSA30, Germany). We form a drop composed of fluorinated oil Novec HFE-7500 (3M, USA) containing 1 wt% of surfactant in millipore water (Synergy, Merck Millipore, Germany) that optionally contains 150 mM or 1 M NaCl (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). We measure the interfacial tension in 1 s intervals. It initially decreases until it reaches a plateau value that we report. Each measurement is repeated at least 3 times to determine the average value and its standard deviation.

2.3. Packing density measurements

The mean molecular area of the surfactants is determined with a Langmuir trough (KN2002, KSV Nima, Biolin Scientific, Finland) using millipore water, water containing 150 mM and 1M NaCl. To measure the surface pressure we use a platinum Wilhelmy plate. To test if the trough and the Wilhelmy plate are clean, we make sure the surface pressure stays below 0.3

mN/m when closing the barriers without adding any surfactant. We dissolve 0.1 wt% of the surfactants in Novec HFE-7100 and slowly add 50 μ l of this solution to the water-air interface. To ensure all the HFE-7100 is evaporated and the surfactants attain their equilibrium conformation, we wait for 8 h if pure water is used, 3 h if water contains 150 mM NaCl and 1 h if water contains 1 M NaCl before we perform the experiments by closing the barriers at a speed of 5 mm/min. We assign the area where the slope of the surface pressure against the mean molecular area clearly decreases for the first time to the minimum area the surfactant occupies without being externally strongly compressed, A , and use this value to calculate the surfactant packing density, $\rho=A^{-1}$.

2.4. Production of PDMS microfluidic chip

We fabricate microfluidic devices from PDMS (Dow Corning, USA) using soft lithography.^[20] To form drops in microfluidic devices, channels must be non-wetting to the inner aqueous phase. To form aqueous drops in a fluorinated oil, we make the channel walls fluorophilic by treating them with a HFE-7500-based solution containing 2 wt% of trichloro(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl)silane (Sigma-Aldrich, USA).

2.5. Production of drops

We produce aqueous drops that are dispersed in HFE-7500 or FC-40 (3M, USA) containing 1 wt% of surfactant. Drops are composed of pure water (MiliQ, Merck, Germany), water containing 20 wt% PEG 6000 Da (Rotipuran, Carl Roth, Germany), water containing 150 mM NaCl, 1 M NaCl, or a mixture of 1 M NaCl and 20 wt% PEG. The two solutions are

injected into the microfluidic device using two volume controlled syringe pumps (Cronus Sigma 1000, Labhut, UK) at flow rates between 1000 $\mu\text{l/h}$ and 4000 $\mu\text{l/h}$.

2.6. Mechanical stability of emulsion drops

To test the mechanical stability of drops we add 30 μl of densely packed drops dispersed in HFE-7500 into a 1 ml Eppendorf tube (VWR, USA). We accelerate the sample for 1 min at room temperature using a centrifuge (VWR microstar 12, Labogene, Denmark) and monitor the drop integrity using optical microscopy. If some of the drops retain their integrity, we repetitively increase the acceleration by 50 g up to a total acceleration of 250 g. If drops still retain their integrity, we further increase the acceleration in steps of 1000 g until all the drops coalesce. We report the acceleration at which all the drops coalesce, because this transition is easier to quantify than the acceleration where the first drops start to coalesce. Each measurement is repeated at least three times, each time using a different batch of drops to obtain an average and standard deviation.

2.7. Temperature stability of emulsion drops

To test the temperature stability of drops, we add 30 μl of densely packed drops dispersed in HFE-7500 into a 1 ml Eppendorf tube (VWR, USA) and incubate the sample at 30°C for 10 min (Thermal Shake Touch, VWR, Denmark). The drop integrity is monitored using optical microscopy and if some drops remain intact, we increase the temperature by 5 °C and incubate them again for 10 min. This procedure is repeated until all drops coalesce and we report this temperature. To calculate the statistics, we repeat each data point at least three times, each time using a different batch of drops.

3. Results and Discussion:

To test the influence of the surfactant composition on the drop stability, we produce aqueous drops with a diameter of $160\ \mu\text{m}$, using PDMS-based microfluidic flow focusing devices,^[21] as shown in **Figure 1**. We use fluorinated oil, HFE-7500, containing 1 wt% surfactant as an outer phase and water containing 20 wt% of PEG6000 as an inner phase; PEG is added to the inner phase to increase its viscosity, thereby facilitating drop formation. To quantify the mechanical stability of drops, we centrifuge them and measure the minimum acceleration that causes all drops to coalesce within 1 min. To quantify the thermal stability of drops, we heat them and measure the minimum temperature where all drops coalesce within 10 min.

Figure 1: (a) Microscope image of water in oil emulsion drops made by a microfluidic flow focusing device. (b) Overview and (c,d) close-up schematic illustrations of water drops dispersed in oil stabilized by (c) triblock and (d) diblock copolymer surfactants.

3.1. Triblock copolymer surfactants

3.1.1. Influence of the PEG length on drop stability

To test if the stability of drops coated with fluorinated block copolymer surfactants depends on the PEG block length, we synthesize two different triblock copolymers. Each of them contains two fluorinated blocks (FSH₂) that are separated by a hydrophilic PEG block, FSH₂-PEG, as shown schematically in **Figure 2a**. One surfactant contains a PEG with a molecular weight of 308 Da, the other one with a molecular weight of 594 Da, as summarized in **Table 1**. The second surfactant closely resembles FSH₂-PEG600, the surfactant, which has been reported to efficiently stabilize aqueous drops in fluorinated oils.^[21] Indeed, this surfactant imparts a higher stability to drops than FSH₂-PEG308, as shown in **Figure 3a**, suggesting that drop stability increases with increasing PEG molecular weight. To test if we can increase drop stability even more by increasing the PEG length, we synthesize FSH₂-PEG5000. Unfortunately, the solubility of this surfactant in HFE-7500 is so low that it precipitates if dispersed at 1 wt% in HFE-7500 at room temperature, resulting in very low drop stability.

Figure 2: The chemical structure of (a) FSH₂-PEG308 and FSH₂-594, (b) FSH₂-Jeffamine600, FSH₂-Jeffamine900 and (c) FSH₂-Jeffamine2000. The chemical structure of (d) FSH-PEG220, and (e) FSH-Jeffamine600, FSH-Jeffamine1000 and FSH-Jeffamine2000. The number of repeat units for each block is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview over the different fluorinated surfactants.

Name	Molecular Weight Hydrophillic Block [g/mol]	Molecular Weight PEG [g/mol]	Repeat Units	Ratio of R_g [-]	γ [mN/m]	ρ [1/nm ²]
FSH ₂ -PEG308	366	308	a=7	0.408	15.8	0.77
FSH ₂ -Jeffamine600	635	396	b+d=3.6, c=9	0.463	10.9	0.62
FSH ₂ -PEG594	600	594	a=13.5	0.570	8.5	0.73
FSH ₂ -Jeffamine900	928	550	b+d=6, c=12.5	0.546	4.3	0.68
FSH ₂ -Jeffamine2000	2094	1716	e+g=6, f=39	0.964	26.1	0.64
FSH-PEG220	278	220	h=5	0.345	10.9	1.17
FSH-Jeffamine600	582	44	i=9, j=1	0.154	9.7	1.03
FSH-Jeffamine1000	1026	836	i=3, j=19	0.672	18.3	2.10
FSH-Jeffamine2000	1962	264	i=29, j=6	0.377	21.8	1.38

Figure 3: Stability of drops coated with surfactants containing PEG blocks with different molecular weights if (a,c) accelerated and (b,d) stored at elevated temperatures. Aqueous drops containing (a, b) 20 wt% PEG6000 and (c, d) 1 M NaCl (filled symbols) or 150 mM NaCl (empty symbols), are stabilized with triblock- (\blacktriangle) and diblock (\blacksquare) copolymers. Drops that did not coalesce at 11400 g, the maximum achievable acceleration, are indicated with the triangles pointing down (\blacktriangledown).

To vary the PEG length over a wider range, we exchange the PEG block with Jeffamine, which is composed of a linear PEG whose two ends are covalently linked to two polypropylene oxide (PPO) blocks, as shown in Figures 2b and 2c. Jeffamine is contained in many of the fluorinated block copolymer surfactants used to stabilize aqueous drops.^[30-32] To test the influence of the PPO blocks on the drop stability, we synthesize a triblock copolymer surfactant with a Jeffamine whose molecular weight is 600 Da; this Jeffamine contains a 396 Da-sized PEG block. Drops coated with this surfactant display a lower stability than those coated with FSH₂-PEG594, as shown in Figure 3a. This result suggests that the volume ratio of PEG to FSH must be optimized to achieve maximum drop stability. To test this suggestion, we synthesize a surfactant containing Jeffamine900 that contains a PEG block with a molecular weight of 550 Da, which is very similar to the PEG contained in FSH₂-PEG594. Indeed, drops coated with this surfactant also display a very high stability; these drops do not coalesce if accelerated up to 11,400 g, which is the highest acceleration our centrifuge can be operated at, as shown in Figure 3a. To test the influence of the PEG length on the drop stability over a wider range, we synthesize surfactants with longer PEG blocks. Drops coated with these surfactants display an inferior stability, as shown in Figure 3a, indicating that there is an optimum PEG length for triblock surfactants, where they stabilize drops most efficiently.

3.1.2. Drop stability at elevated temperatures

Many biological applications require drops to be stable at elevated temperatures. To test if good mechanical drop stability translates into good temperature stability, we visualize drops after they have been stored at different temperatures for 10 min using optical microscopy.

Drops stabilized with FSH₂-Jeffamine900 display the highest stability if stored at elevated temperatures: They only coalesce when stored for 10 min at 62 °C or above, as shown in Figure 3b. By contrast, drops stabilized with FSH₂-594 and FSH₂-Jeffamine600 only remain intact up to 50 °C and those stabilized with all the other tested surfactants already coalesce at 40 °C or below. These results indicate that drops that display a high mechanical stability also display a high temperature stability. Moreover, the PPO blocks contained in Jeffamine900 positively affect drop stability if the volume ratio of PEG to FSH is optimized.

To relate the optimum hydrophilic block length to the length of the entire surfactant, we compute the ratio of the radius of gyration of PEG, $R_g(\text{PEG})$, to that of the hydrophobic block, $R_g(\text{FSH})$, assuming both blocks are dispersed in theta solvents, as detailed in the supporting information. We use this ratio instead of the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value because HLB values are measures for the weight percentage of the hydrophilic block in relation to the total molecular weight of the surfactant. Because the molecular weight of a fluorinated block is much higher than that of a hydrocarbon-based block with a similar number of carbon atoms, the HLB value will be much lower than that of hydrocarbon-containing surfactants with similar volume ratios. We find that triblock surfactants with a ratio $R_g(\text{PEG})/R_g(\text{FSH})$ of 0.56 impart the best stability to drops, as shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: Influence of the ratio of the radii of gyration of PEG to FSH on the stability of aqueous drops containing 20% PEG coated with di- (■) and triblock (▲) copolymers. (a) The mechanical stability of drops coated with different surfactants, measured as the maximum acceleration, a , drops can sustain. Drops that did not coalesce at the maximum acceleration

we could achieve are represented by triangles that point down (▼). (b) Temperature, T , when all drops coalesced as a function of the ratio of the radii of gyration of PEG to FSH.

3.1.3. Influence of fluid viscosity on drop stability

If drops are employed as vessels to conduct PCR reactions or for cell encapsulation, they often contain no or only low concentrations of polymers. In these cases, the viscosity of the aqueous phase is lower than what we studied so far. To investigate the influence of the viscosity of the inner phase on the drop stability, we produce aqueous drops that do not contain any free PEG or any other additives. Pure aqueous drops, whose viscosity is 3 times lower than that of drops containing 20 wt% PEG, also display the highest stability if coated with FSH₂-Jeffamine900, as shown in **Figure S10**. Indeed, the stabilities for pure aqueous drops coated with any of the tested surfactants are very similar to those of PEG-containing drops, indicating that the viscosity of the inner phase does not significantly influence the drop stability. To test if the viscosity of the outer phase affects drop stability, we produce aqueous drops contained in another fluorinated oil, FC-40 (3M, USA), schematically shown in **Figure S11**, whose viscosity is almost three times higher than that of HFE-7500. Also in this case, the drop stability is very similar, as shown in **Figure S12**, indicating that drop stability does not strongly depend on the viscosity of the inner and outer fluids.

3.1.4. Influence of salt on drop stability

Solutions that mimic physiologic conditions contain salts. Salts do not strongly influence the fluid viscosity, but they lower the solubility of PEG in water,^[33] thereby often reducing the effectiveness of surfactants to stabilize emulsion drops. To test the influence of salt on the stability of drops coated with fluorinated surfactants, we produce aqueous drops containing 150 mM NaCl. Salt-containing drops display a much lower stability than their salt-free

counterparts: Most of them rupture at accelerations below 400 g and at temperatures below 50°C as shown in Figures 3c and 3d. We expect this reduced drop stability to be caused by the reduced PEG solubility. To test if PEG further collapses if dissolved in aqueous solutions containing higher salt concentrations, we produce aqueous drops containing 1M NaCl. Interestingly, the stability of these drops is very similar to that of drops containing 150 mM NaCl, as shown in Figure 3c. These results suggest that PEG is already strongly collapsed in the presence of 150 mM NaCl. Consequently, the stability of drops containing 150 mM NaCl is similarly low as that of drops containing much higher salt concentrations. Their stability significantly increases, if they contain next to 1 M NaCl also 20 wt% of free PEG6000, as shown in **Figure S13**. These results indicate that free PEG reduces the collapse of the PEG contained in the surfactants and therefore, increases the stability of salt-containing drops. Nevertheless, their stability is much lower than that of salt-free drops. Remarkably, drops containing high salt concentrations display the best temperature-stability if coated with the surfactant that has the shortest PEG block we tested, as shown in Figure 3. These results indicate that the optimum ratio of the radii of gyration of PEG to FSH depends on the conformation of the blocks.

3.1.5. Influence of the PEG length on the interfacial tension

To investigate the reason for the different stabilities of drops coated with different surfactants, we quantify the tension of water-HFE-7500 interfaces, γ , in the presence of the different triblock copolymer surfactants. Emulsion drops tend to coalesce to reduce the interfacial area, A , and thereby the interfacial energy $E_\gamma = \gamma * A$. Because E_γ scales with γ , the drop stability often scales with γ .^[34,35] To test if this is also the case for the surfactants

investigated here, we measure γ as a function of the PEG molecular weight of the different surfactants, as shown in **Figure 5a**.

Figure 5: Influence of the PEG molecular weight on the interfacial tension (γ) and the surfactant packing density (ρ). (a) The interfacial tensions between HFE-7500 and drops composed of pure water stabilized with triblock- (\blacktriangle) and diblock (\blacksquare) surfactants are shown as a function of the molecular weight of PEG contained in the surfactants. (b) Packing densities of triblock- (\blacktriangle) and diblock (\blacksquare) surfactants at the interface of water without any salt with air (filled symbols) and that of water containing 150 mM NaCl (\diamond) and 1M NaCl (\square) with air are shown as a function of the PEG molecular weight. As a reference, we include the packing density of pure FSH, Krytox, at the interface or air with pure water (\bullet), water containing 150 mM NaCl (\diamond), and 1M NaCl (\circ)

The interfacial tension decreases with increasing PEG molecular weight until it reaches a minimum of 4.3 mN/m for surfactants comprising Jeffamine900, which contains PEG550. If the PEG molecular weight is further increased, the interfacial tension strongly increases, as shown in Figure 5a. Remarkably, γ is two times lower if interfaces are coated with FSH₂-Jeffamine900, than if they are coated with FSH₂-PEG594, even though these two surfactants have the same PEG length and hence, the same ratio of the radii of gyration of PEG to FSH. These results indicate that the PPO blocks contribute to the reduction of the interfacial tension. The minimum tension of interfaces coated with Jeffamine900 correlates well with the highest stability measured for drops coated with this surfactant, as shown in **Figure 6**. Indeed, the stability of salt-free drops coated with triblock copolymers scales with interfacial tension, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Interfacial tension (γ) of di- (■) and triblock (▲) copolymer surfactants as a function of the (a) mechanical and (b) temperature stability of drops. Drops that did not coalesce at the maximum acceleration we could achieve are represented by triangles that point down (▼).

3.1.6. Influence of the PEG length on surfactant packing density

The interfacial tension is usually thought to scale with the surfactant packing density.^[36] To test if this correlation also holds for the triblock copolymers investigated here, we quantify the surfactant packing density at the water-air interface using a Langmuir trough. We assume the surfactant packing density at the water-air interface to be similar to that at the water-HFE-7500 interface if the PEG is the packing density-limiting block. By contrast, if FSH is the packing density-limiting block at the water-air, we do not expect to see any influence of the PEG molecular weight on the surfactant packing density. In this case, we cannot correlate the surfactant packing density measured with the Langmuir trough to that at the water-HFE-7500 interface. By measuring the packing density as a function of the PEG molecular weight, we should be able to clearly distinguish these two cases. We measure the surface pressure as a function of the area occupied by a surfactant molecule and convert it into a packing density, assuming the surface pressure scales with the surfactant packing density. The surface

pressure increases with increasing surfactant packing density until it reaches a plateau. Upon further compression, the surface pressure usually rapidly decreases, which is assigned to a collapse of the monolayer.^[37] However, in our case, the surface pressure remains almost constant, as shown in **Figure S15**. This could indicate that at this pressure, some of the surfactants form water-soluble aggregates, establishing equilibrium between surfactants at the water-air interface and in solution. We approximate the molecular area at the onset of this plateau as the minimum area a surfactant occupies at the water-air interface and use this value to calculate the maximum packing density. The packing density of triblock copolymers at the water-air interface is independent of PEG molecular weight, as shown in Figure 5b. These results indicate that the collapsed FSH blocks are packing density limiting. Hence, for triblock copolymers, the correlation between interfacial tension and surfactant packing density at the water-HFE-7500 interface remains unclear.

3.2. Diblock copolymer surfactants

3.2.1. Influence of PEG length on drop stability

The surfactant packing density at liquid-liquid interfaces is usually higher for diblock than triblock copolymers,^[38] as schematically illustrated in Figures 1c and 1d. To test, if we can increase drop stability by increasing the surfactant packing density, we synthesize diblock copolymers composed of a FSH block covalently linked to a hydrophilic block and vary the PEG molecular weight between 44 Da and 836 Da. From all the tested diblock copolymers, FSH-Jeffamine 1000, which has a PEG molecular weight of 836 Da, imparts the highest stability to drops, as shown in Figure 3. Interestingly, this surfactant has a ratio of the radii of gyration of PEG to FSH of 0.67, a value that is very similar to the optimum value determined for triblock copolymers. However, the stability of drops coated with diblock copolymer

surfactants is in all cases inferior to that of drops coated with triblock copolymer counterparts that have a similar PEG length, as shown in Figure 3.

3.2.2. Influence of PEG length on interfacial tension

To investigate the reason for the lower stability of drops coated with diblock copolymers we quantify the water-HFE-7500 interfacial tension using pendant drop measurements. Diblock copolymers lower the interfacial tension to a smaller extent than triblock copolymers with a similar PEG molecular weight, as shown in Figure 5. This might be a contributing reason for the lower stability of drops coated with diblock surfactants. Interestingly, the stability of drops coated with diblock surfactants, does not scale with the interfacial tension, as shown in Figure 6. This is in strong contrast to the commonly assumed direct correlation between the interfacial tension and drop stability and to the correlation measured here for drops coated with triblock surfactants. This result indicates that there is another parameter that more strongly influences the stability of drops coated with diblock copolymers.

3.2.3. Influence of the PEG length on surfactant packing density

Block copolymer surfactants self-assemble at liquid-liquid interfaces of drops, thereby imparting a steric stabilization layer to them. The thickness of this steric stabilization layer scales with the surfactant packing density.^[39] Hence, we would expect the drop stability to scale with the surfactant packing density. To test this expectation, we quantify the packing density of diblock copolymers at the water-air interface. For diblock copolymers, the surfactant packing density at the water-air interface increases with decreasing PEG molecular weight and reaches the lowest value for FSH-Jeffamine600, which contains the shortest PEG we tested; this surfactant contains only a single ethylene glycol repeat unit, whose molecular

weight is 44 Da. Indeed, the packing density of FSH-Jeffamine600 is very similar to that of pure FSH, as shown in Figure 5b. These results indicate that for diblock copolymers containing more than one ethylene glycol unit, PEG is the packing density limiting block. Thus, we expect the packing density of these diblock copolymers at the water-HFE-7500 interface to be similar to that measured at the water-air interface. Interestingly, the stability of drops coated with diblock copolymers increases with increasing surfactant packing density as shown in **Figure 7**. These results indicate that for these diblock copolymer surfactants, a high surfactant packing density is more important than a low interfacial tension for obtaining good drop stability.

Figure 7: The stability of drops coated with diblock surfactants if (a) accelerated and (b) subjected to elevated temperatures (T) as a function of the surfactant packing density.

3.2.3. Influence of salt on drop stability

To test the influence of salts on the stability of drops coated with diblock copolymers, we produce aqueous drops containing 150 mM NaCl. Also in this case, salts strongly reduce the drop stability, as shown by the empty symbols in Figure 3c and 3d. The drop stability remains nearly unchanged if the salt concentration is increased to 1 M, by analogy to the stability of drops coated with triblock copolymers. The correlation of the drop stability with

the dispersant packing density, observed for salt-free drops, also holds for drops containing 1 M NaCl, as shown in Figure S16. However, while salt-free drops are most efficiently stabilized with triblock copolymers, salt-containing drops are most stable if coated with diblock copolymers. These results indicate that salt-containing drops are most efficiently stabilized with surfactants that pack most densely.

4. Conclusion

We study the influence of the PEG molecular weight of nonionic di- and triblock copolymer surfactants on their ability to stabilize aqueous drops in fluorinated oils. The stability of drops coated with triblock copolymers scales with the interfacial tension whereas that of drops coated with diblock copolymers scales with the surfactant packing density. The stability of aqueous, salt-free drops is highest if coated with the triblock copolymer FSH₂-Jeffamine900, whose ratio $R_g(\text{PEG})/R_g(\text{FSH})$ is 0.56; this surfactant lowers the water-HFE-7500 interfacial tension most. By contrast, the stability of salt-containing drops is highest if coated with the diblock copolymer FSH-Jeffamine2000, the surfactant that packs most densely. These results indicate that the choice of the most appropriate surfactant depends on the exact composition of the fluids. Our results provide guidelines for the synthesis of new surfactants that impart good stability to drops if subjected to demanding conditions.

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References

- [1] W. J. Duncanson, T. Lin, A. R. Abate, S. Seiffert, R. K. Shah, D. A. Weitz, *Lab Chip* **2012**, *12*, 2135.
- [2] B. J. Hindson, K. D. Ness, D. A. Masquelier, P. Belgrader, N. J. Heredia, A. J. Makarewicz, I. J. Bright, M. Y. Lucero, A. L. Hiddessen, T. C. Legler, T. K. Kitano, M. R. Hodel, J. F. Petersen, P. W. Wyatt, E. R. Steenblock, P. H. Shah, L. J. Bousse, C. B. Troup, J. C. Mellen, D. K. Wittmann, N. G. Erndt, T. H. Cauley, R. T. Koehler, A. P. So, S. Dube, K. A. Rose, L. Montesclaros, S. Wang, D. P. Stumbo, S. P. Hodges, S. Romine, F. P. Milanovich, H. E. White, J. F. Regan, G. A. Karlin-Neumann, C. M. Hindson, S. Saxonov, un B. W. Colston, *Anal. Chem.* **2011**, *83*, 8604.
- [3] A. D. Griffiths, D. S. Tawfik, *Trends Biotechnol.* **2006**, *24*, 395.
- [4] D. S. Tawfik, A. D. Griffiths, *Nat. Biotechnol.* **1998**, *16*, 652.
- [5] J. Clausell-Tormos, D. Lieber, J. C. Baret, A. El-Harrak, O. J. Miller, L. Frenz, J. Blouwolff, K. J. Humphry, S. Köster, H. Duan, C. Holtze, D. A. Weitz, A. D. Griffiths, un C. A. Merten, *Chem. Biol.*, **2008**, *15*, 427.
- [6] A. M. Klein, L. Mazutis, I. Akartuna, N. Tallapragada, A. Veres, V. Li, L. Peshkin, D. A. Weitz, un M. W. Kirschner, *Cell*, **2015**, *161*, 1187.
- [7] A. Rotem, O. Ram, N. Shores, R. A. Sperling, A. Goren, D. A. Weitz, un B. E. Bernstein, *Nat. Biotechnol.*, **2015**, *33*, 1165.
- [8] A. Rotem, O. Ram, N. Shores, R. A. Sperling, M. Schnall-Levin, H. Zhang, A. Basu, B. E. Bernstein, un D. A. Weitz, *PLoS One*, **2015**, *10*, 1.
- [9] A. E. Fischer, S. K. Wu, J. B. G. Proescher, A. Rotem, C. B. Chang, H. Zhang, Y. Tao, T. S. Mehoke, P. M. Thielen, A. O. Kolawole, T. J. Smith, C. E. Wobus, D. A. Weitz, J. S. Lin, A. B. Feldman, un J. T. Wolfe, *J. Virol. Methods*, **2015**, *213*, 111.
- [10] Y. Tao, A. Rotem, H. Zhang, C. B. Chang, A. Basu, A. O. Kolawole, S. A. Koehler, Y. Ren, J. S. Lin, J. M. Pipas, A. B. Feldman, C. E. Wobus, un D. A. Weitz, *Lab Chip*, **2015**, *15*, 3934.
- [11] Y. Tao, A. Rotem, H. Zhang, S. K. Cockrell, S. A. Koehler, C. B. Chang, L. W. Ung, P. G. Cantalupo, Y. Ren, J. S. Lin, A. B. Feldman, C. E. Wobus, J. M. Pipas, un D. A. Weitz, *ChemBioChem*, **2015**, *16*, 2167.

- [12] H. Zhang, S. K. Cockrell, A. O. Kolawole, A. Rotem, A. W. R. Serohijos, C. B. Chang, Y. Tao, T. S. Mehoke, Y. Han, J. S. Lin, N. S. Giacobbi, A. B. Feldman, E. Shakhnovich, D. A. Weitz, C. E. Wobus, un J. M. Pipas, *J. Virol.*, **2015**, 89, 7722.
- [13] A. S. Utada, L.-Y. Chu, A. Fernandez-Nieves, D. R. Link, C. Holtze, D. A. Weitz, *MRS Bull.* **2007**, 32, 702.
- [14] H. Song, D. L. Chen, R. F. Ismagilov, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2006**, 45, 7336.
- [15] L. S. Roach, H. Song, R. F. Ismagilov, *Anal. Chem.* **2005**, 77, 785.
- [16] K. C. Lowe, *J. Fluor. Chem.* **2002**, 118, 19.
- [17] K. C. Lowe, *J. Fluor. Chem.* **2001**, 109, 59.
- [18] J.-C. Baret, *Lab Chip* **2012**, 12, 422.
- [19] J. N. Lee, C. Park, G. M. Whitesides, *Anal. Chem.* **2003**, 75, 6544.
- [20] Y. Xia, G. M. Whitesides, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **1998**, 37, 550.
- [21] C. Holtze, A. C. Rowat, J. J. Agresti, J. B. Hutchison, F. E. Angilè, C. H. J. Schmitz, S. Köster, H. Duan, K. J. Humphry, R. A. Scanga, J. S. Johnson, D. Pisignano, un D. A. Weitz, *Lab Chip*, **2008**, 8, 1632.
- [22] O. Wagner, J. Thiele, M. Weinhart, L. Mazutis, D. A. Weitz, W. T. S. Huck, R. Haag, *Lab Chip* **2016**, 16, 65.
- [23] S. C. Kim, D. J. Sukovich, A. R. Abate, *Lab Chip* **2015**, 15, 3163.
- [24] RAN Biotechnologies, www.ranbiotechnologies.com, accessed: April, 2016.
- [25] S. Utech, R. Prodanovic, A. S. Mao, R. Ostafe, D. J. Mooney, D. A. Weitz, *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* **2015**, 4, 1628.
- [26] L. R. Arriaga, E. Amstad, D. A. Weitz, *Lab Chip* **2015**, 15, 3335.
- [27] M. J. Hey, S. M. Ilett, G. Davidson, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans* **1995**, 91, 3897.
- [28] S. Seiffert, D. A. Weitz, *Soft Matter* **2010**, 6, 3184.
- [29] B. Malisova, S. Tosatti, M. Textor, K. Gademann, S. Zürcher, *Langmuir* **2010**, 26, 4018.
- [30] J.-U. Shim, R. T. Ranasinghe, C. A. Smith, S. M. Ibrahim, F. Hollfelder, W. T. S. Huck, D. Klenerman, C. Abell, *ACS Nano* **2013**, 7, 5955.
- [31] M. Lee, J. W. Collins, D. M. Aubrecht, R. A. Sperling, L. Solomon, J.-W. Ha, G.-R. Yi, D. A. Weitz, V. N. Manoharan, *Lab Chip* **2014**, 14, 509.
- [32] C. J. DeJournette, J. Kim, H. Medlen, X. Li, L. J. Vincent, C. J. Easley, *Anal. Chem.* **2013**, 85, 10556.
- [33] P. Alexandridis, J. F. Holzwarth, *Langmuir* **1997**, 13, 6074.
- [34] M. Bourrel, A. Graciaa, R. S. Schechter, W. H. Wade, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **1979**, 72, 161.
- [35] H.-J. Butt, K. Graf, M. Kappl, *Physics and Chemistry of Interfaces*, Wiley-VCH.

Weinheim **2003**.

- [36] G. T. Barnes, I. R. Gentle, *Interfacial Science: an introduction*, 2nd ed, Oxford University Press, New York, USA **2011**.
- [37] R. A. Hann, *Langmuir-Blodgett Films*, Springer, Berlin, **1990**.
- [38] J. Song, W. E. Krause, O. J. Rojas, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2014**, *420*, 174.
- [39] S. J. Sofia, V. Premnath, E. W. Merrill, *Macromolecules* **1998**, *31*, 5059.

Table of Contents entry:

We investigate the stability of aqueous drops dispersed in fluorinated oils. The stability of drops coated with triblock copolymers scales with the interfacial tension. By contrast, the stability of drops coated with diblock copolymers scales with their packing density at the liquid-liquid interface.

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Influence of Fluorinated Surfactant Composition on the Stability of Emulsion Drops